

Promoting Successful and Sustainable Community Dialogue Outcomes: A Practitioner's Toolkit for Zimbabwe

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This toolkit is designed to promote successful and sustainable outcomes for community dialogues in Zimbabwe. It builds on findings from 13 cases of community dialogue conducted across the country between 2018 and 2023, all of which are examined in the IFIT report, [Promoting Bottom-Up Dialogue: A Study of Community-Level Dialogue Experiences in Zimbabwe](#).

The findings are complemented by contributions from Zimbabwean experts and community-based and civil society organisations engaged in convening community dialogues across the country, namely the Institute for Local Governance (ILG), Youth Empowerment and Transformation Trust (YETT), Community Youth In Development Trust (CYDT), Youth in Peace Building Initiative Trust (YIPIT), Zimbabwe Women Against Corruption Trust (ZWACT) and The Zimbabwe Association of Community Radio Stations (ZACRAS).

By emphasising strategies that foster active participation and alternative approaches to conflict resolution, this toolkit helps equip communities to devise solutions grounded in important lessons and concepts identified through IFIT's research. It underscores the unifying power of dialogue, helping inspire communities to come together around a shared vision for their future.

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1 What is community dialogue?

A forum, meeting or convening that draws participants from various sections of a community and creates the opportunity for exchanging information and perspectives, clarifying viewpoints, and developing solutions to issues of interest to the community.

2 How can dialogue transform communities?

Dialogue is crucial for community- and nation-building, fostering unity and empowering individuals and communities alike to tackle challenges through shared understanding. Dialogue is also a sustainable method of building and sustaining peace within communities.

3 Who can use this toolkit?

- Community leaders (Chiefs, village heads and other leaders)
- Community members
- Local government officials (Councillors)
- National government officials (Parliamentarians and other public officials)
- Community-based organisations (CBOs) and civil society organisations (CSOs)
- Dialogue practitioners
- Faith-based institutions and organisations (FBOs)
- Business councils and associations
- Academic institutions and experts

4 What to consider before you start?

Understand the Community

- Every community is different and has unique demographics, interests and experiences.
- Recognise that each community will have its own social norms, spiritual beliefs, and cultural values.
- Identify key entry points for dialogue, such as traditional leaders, local authority representatives, community leaders, and civil society organisations.
- Consider the historical, political, cultural, economic, and social contexts that may influence the community's perspectives and participation in dialogue.
- Map relevant stakeholders to ensure inclusive, comprehensive and meaningful engagement.

Understand the Issue

An issue is a significant challenge or problem that affects different groups in a community in various ways. Addressing it requires thoughtful discussion and thorough analysis to develop effective solutions.

- Facilitate a process for community members to identify the issue they want to address.
- Recognise that an issue may take various forms, and communities respond differently based on their unique experiences.

Don't delay important conversations!

Waiting for ideal conditions can delay dialogue. Communities should seize the opportunity for dialogue and address issues in real time, as the window of opportunity may be brief or lost.

5 What are the main types of dialogue?

Types

Consultation

A participatory process where community members share their views on a challenge and propose solutions.

Pros

- Encourages inclusivity and ownership.
- Provides diverse perspectives.
- Increases legitimacy and acceptance of outcomes.

Cons

- Can be time-consuming and resource-intensive.
- Risk of “fatigue” if too extensive.
- No guarantee input will be implemented.
- Vocal groups may dominate.

Mediation

A process where a mediator helps parties reach a friendly settlement to a dispute.

- Neutral and capacitated mediator supports resolution.
- Final decision remains with the community.
- Encourages mutual understanding and collaboration.

- Power imbalances may affect outcomes.
- Mediator's skill and neutrality are crucial.

Negotiation

Direct discussions between parties aimed at resolving a dispute.

- Parties shape the outcome directly.
- Encourages mutual understanding and compromise.
- May be faster and more flexible.

- Power imbalances may lead to unfair outcomes.
- If no agreement is reached, divisions may be exacerbated.

6 What are the main discussion formats?

Types

Round table

To facilitate discussions among various speakers and topics to gather diverse perspectives and hear community voices.

Pros

- Encourages equal participation and open exchange of ideas.
- Fosters a collaborative and inclusive environment.
- Allows diverse perspectives to be shared and considered.
- Helps build consensus and mutual understanding.

Cons

- Can be time-consuming with many participants.
- Risk of dominant voices overshadowing others.
- May lack clear decision-making mechanisms or follow-up actions.
- Requires skilled facilitation to remain focused and productive.

Town hall

To present ideas formally while allowing participants to share opinions and engage in a Q&A plenary session.

- Provides a platform for formal idea presentation and discussion.
- Encourages broad community participation.
- Allows for direct interaction between community members and decision-makers.
- Facilitates transparency and accountability in decision-making.

- Can become one-sided if dominated by a few voices.
- Limited time for in-depth discussions.
- May not lead to concrete actions or decisions.
- Requires strong facilitation to stay productive.
- Large groups can make engagement challenging.

Open discussions

To encourage idea exploration and allow new issues to be introduced and examined collaboratively.

- Encourages free expression of ideas and perspectives.
- Allows new issues to emerge organically.
- Promotes collaborative problem-solving.
- Fosters a more inclusive and dynamic conversation.

- Can become unfocused without clear structure.
- Risk of dominant voices overpowering others.
- May lack concrete outcomes or action points.
- Requires skilled facilitation to keep discussions productive.
- Can be time-consuming with no clear resolution.

7 Who are some key actors?

Government Departments

Community dialogues in Zimbabwe require government support and security sector approval. Convenors must ensure transparency and engage relevant local authorities to obtain the necessary approval and clearance before gathering the community.

Community Leaders

Community leaders are figures of influence and authority who can lend support and credibility to dialogue processes. When the convener is not a community leader, it is essential to involve them from the beginning. They play a key role in mobilising participation and ensuring the implementation of dialogue outcomes.

Convenors

Community dialogues must be led by a trusted convener who can effectively mobilise the community around key issues. The convener's responsibilities include organising the meeting and inviting participants. Convenors should identify centres of power and trusted figures within the community to build relationships.

Facilitators

Facilitators are responsible for creating a safe environment where participants can raise issues, share ideas, and exchange perspectives. While the convener can also serve as the facilitator, they must be trained to effectively guide conversations and address any barriers or challenges that arise.

Community Members

Community dialogues should be centred around community members, as they provide valuable insights into the issues affecting their community. They must take the lead in shaping the agenda and fully commit to the process to support and implement its outcomes.

Dialogue Champions

Dialogue champions are community members who actively promote the dialogue's cause by mobilising their peers, encouraging participation, and shaping narratives within the broader community.

8 How to engage key leaders and decision-makers?

Engaging key leaders and decision-makers early accelerates decision-making towards solutions, facilitates the implementation of agreements, and strengthens ownership of both the process and outcomes. Their early involvement fosters commitment to translating dialogue recommendations into action. Identifying the right leaders and decision-makers—along with the governance structures they represent—is therefore essential for fostering meaningful dialogue and driving sustainable change within communities.

Provinces of Zimbabwe

10 provinces
64 districts
1970 wards

Based on 2025 data

1. Matabeleland North
2. Bulawayo

3. Matabeleland South
4. Mashonaland West

5. Midlands
6. Masvingo

7. Harare
8. Mashonaland Central

9. Mashonaland East
10. Manicaland

Understanding Zimbabwe's Government Structures for engaging leaders

Level	Traditional Governance Structure	National and Local Governance Structure
National	<p>Chief Council President of the National Council of Chiefs. A member of the Senate and an appointee of the Council (which is an assembly of traditional leaders from throughout Zimbabwe)</p>	<p>Member of Parliament Elected through National Elections to the National Assembly</p> <p>Minister Appointed by the President</p> <p>Permanent Secretary of the Ministry Appointed by the President</p> <p>Chairperson of a Parliamentary Portfolio Committee Established under the Constitution and Standing Order and Rules of Parliament. Appointed in a process of consultation and negotiation within political parties</p>
Provincial	<p>Representative of the Chief Traditional leader that is appointed under customary law</p>	<p>Senator Elected through National Elections to the Senate</p> <p>Provincial Governor Appointed by the President</p> <p>Provincial Administrator Appointed by the Public Service Commission</p>
District	<p>Chief (Mambo) A hereditary position, but the appointment is made official by the president</p>	<p>District Administrator Appointed by the Public Service Commission</p> <p>Rural District Development Council (Chief Executive Officer) Appointed by the RDDC and approved by the Minister</p>
Ward	<p>Headman (SaDunhu) Nominated by the chief then appointed by the Minister of Local Government or Kraal head (a traditional leader that is subordinate to the Chief)</p>	<p>Councillor/ Local Authority Representative Elected through National Elections</p> <p>Ward Development Committee Representatives Elected by the village assembly</p>
Village	<p>Head (SaBhuku) Nominated by Headman upon approval of Chief then appointed by Permanent Secretary of Ministry of Local Government</p>	<p>Village Development Committee Representatives Elected by the village assembly</p>

9 What are the elements of a framework for effective community dialogue?

Planning and agenda setting

- Develop the agenda through consultations with key stakeholders, ensuring community members are the primary drivers.
- Be flexible and adapt the agenda as new concerns or issues arise.

Choosing a location

- Select a safe, familiar environment where participants feel secure and comfortable to engage freely and constructively.

Setting ground rules

- Start by emphasizing the importance of ground rules for a productive dialogue.
- Work with participants to identify and agree on key ground rules, displaying them in the meeting space.
- Refer back to the ground rules as needed to guide conversations.

Vision Casting and setting objectives

- Facilitate a community envisioning exercise to identify shared values and aspirations for an ideal community.
- Document and share the shared vision with participants to inspire ongoing collaboration.

Evaluation and Feedback

- Gather feedback from participants and the broader community through surveys, follow-ups, or informal discussions.
- Use the feedback to assess the dialogue's impact and refine future processes.

Post Dialogue Actions

- Collaboratively outline clear action points, assigning responsibilities to specific individuals or groups.
- Define timelines and expectations to ensure accountability for implementation.

Documentation and Updates

- Use effective communication channels, such as community boards or social media, to share dialogue updates regularly. Regular feedback and updates prevent loss of interest in implementing dialogue outcomes.
- Reach out to key stakeholders who could not attend and communicate the dialogue outcomes to maintain momentum.

Facilitation and Moderation

- Ensure facilitators are well-trained in dialogue facilitation techniques and frameworks, with a solid understanding of diverse dialogue mechanisms.

10 What are the common barriers and challenges?

- Barriers are an inevitable part of any community dialogue. Proactively address these challenges by creating a risk matrix to identify potential risks, evaluate their impact, and plan effective mitigation measures.

An example of a risk matrix is shown below and should be customized for the specific dialogue to assess all possible risks and develop mitigation strategies:

Risk	Likelihood	Impact	Mitigation Measures	Responsible Party
Low attendance or engagement	Medium	High	Conduct outreach through trusted community leaders; send reminders; provide incentives like food or transport.	Convenors Community leaders Dialogue Champions
Logistical challenges	Low	High	Plan logistics thoroughly; choose accessible locations; ensure necessary resources are available.	Convenors
External Interference	High	High	Engage local authorities for approvals; Engage local police	Convenors
Conflict among participants	High	Medium	Establish clear ground rules; train facilitators in conflict management	Facilitator

11 Keys to Sustaining Long Term Impact

Always allow communities to drive the agenda and not merely participate in the dialogues as this builds ownership and accountability.

Regularly update all stakeholders on the status of the implementation of agreed actions.

Facilitate a smooth transfer of responsibility between the dialogue stage and the implementation stage by supporting collaboration between the convenor, implementers and community members.

Highlight successes and address any challenges to maintain transparency and engagement.